

A Rapid Method of Analysis of Halo-Nitrosyl Complexes of Rhenium

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The hydrogen combustion technique of Ter Meulen has been effectively modified and extended to the analysis of nitric oxide-halogen complexes of rhenium. The analysis of a variety of compounds show that simultaneous determination of rhenium, alkali metals, nitric oxide along with several organic amines and halogens is possible in a single determination.

The simple and elegant method of analysis of halogens in organic compounds due to Ter Meulen¹ can be very effectively modified and extended to the analysis of nitric oxide-halogen complexes of metals. In this laboratory we have applied this method for the analysis of a variety of rhenium complexes. The novelty of the method exists in the simultaneous determination of rhenium, alkali metals, nitric oxide and several organic amines along with the halogen.

The original method of Ter Meulen consists of heating the sample containing chlorine in dry hydrogen gas whereby hydrogen chloride is formed quantitatively which is chased by the stream of hydrogen gas and determined afterwards as silver chloride. It has been observed by the present investigators that heating of chloro-nitrosyl-complexes of rhenium under such condition converts the nitric oxide to ammonia and rhenium to the metallic state. Ammonia formed by the reduction of nitric oxide is obtained as ammonium chloride in the form of a white sublimate. If the compound contains organic amines like pyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl etc., these are obtained as their hydrochlorides in the sublimate along with the ammonium chloride. Bromo complexes can also be analysed by the same technique but if the molecule contains organic amines, their hydrobromides partially escape sublimation. In these complexes, therefore, only the total bromine can be determined. In case where the complex contains no halogen the nitric oxide is expelled as free ammonia by reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrogen gas to be used in these experiments should be scrupulously free from oxygen. For this purpose, the hydrogen gas obtained from Zn-H₂SO₄ Kipp's apparatus is passed through two scrubbers containing acidic and alkaline potassium permanganate solution for purification. It is then passed through a long packing of red-hot copper gauze. The gas is finally washed with concentrated sulphuric acid and led into the combustion tube.

Weighed quantity of the sample is taken in a tared porcelain boat and is placed inside a quartz tube. Hydrogen gas is passed through the tube till it is free from air. The boat is then gradually heated to the desired temperature. The decomposition temperature of various compounds vary widely. The decomposition takes place in the following manner:

Estimation of rhenium and alkali metals : After the reaction is over, the boat is cooled and weighed. This gives the total weight of rhenium and alkali halides (only rhenium if alkali metals are absent). The content of the boat is then extracted with oxygen free water and the alkali halide content of the extract is determined gravimetrically as silver halide. From the difference, quantity of rhenium is calculated. The rhenium so obtained is also estimated electrogravimetrically by its conversion into perrhenic acid.

Estimation of ammonium halide and organic amine hydrohalide : These are obtained as sublimate in the cooler part of the combustion tube. The tube, after removal of the boat, is thoroughly washed with water and the halide content of this washing is estimated as before. This gives the total quantity of ammonia and organic amine present. In absence of organic amines, the halide content corresponds to the ammonia (i.e. nitric oxide in the molecule).

Estimation of total halogen : A portion of the halogen is chased out of the tube as hydrogen halide. It is passed through a dilute silver nitrate solution containing a few drops of nitric acid. After the reaction is over, the precipitated silver halide is filtered and weighed. The sum total of all silver halides gives the total halogen in the compound. In case of bromo compounds containing organic amines, the washings of the sublimate is taken along with the hydrogen halide absorbed in the silver nitrate solution and the total silver halide is weighed.

Estimation of free ammonia : In absence of any halogen, the nitric oxide is ultimately driven out as free ammonia gas. It is passed through a known excess of standard sulphuric acid and determined as usual.

Precaution : Care should be taken in the experiment so that the alkali halide in the boat may not volatilise and the sublimate in the tube may not be carried out due to insufficient cooling.

RESULTS

Analysis of a few typical compounds are shown below which have been analysed otherwise to establish their identity.

TABLE

Compounds	Decomposition Temperature °C	Residue in the boat, per cent	Halogen in sublimate, per cent	Halogen liberated as hydrogen halide, per cent	Halogen in the residue in the boat, per cent
$K_2[ReCl_6]$	360	70.6 (70.3)	—	30.0 (29.8)	14.7 (14.9)
$Cs_2[ReCl_5(NO)]$	350	84.8* (79.3)	5.6 (5.4)	10.5 (10.8)	11.3 (10.8)
$Cs_2[ReBr_5(NO)]$	350	68.8 (69.3)	9.0 (9.1)	18.0 (18.1)	18.3 (18.1)
$K_2[ReCl_5(NO)]$	350	71.3 (71.1)	6.4 (7.5)	16.5 (15.0)	15.1 (15.0)
$[ReCl_3py_2(NO)]$	red heat	38.0 (38.7)	22.5 (22.5)	—	—
$[ReCl_3(dipy)(NO)]_x$	red heat	38.1 (38.9)	13.6 (14.8)	7.8 (7.4)	—
$[ReBr_3(dipy)(NO)]$	red heat	30.9 (30.4)	23.6 (26.1)	15.4 (13.1)	—
$[ReCl_3(phen)(NO)]$	red heat	36.8 (37.0)	12.9 (13.8)	7.1 (6.9)	—
$[Re(OH)_3(NO)] \cdot H_2O$	280	66.0 (65.3)	—	4.8** (4.9)	—

Figures in parentheses are required percentages.

* High result probably due to hygroscopic nature of halide.

** Nitrogen percentage.

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REFERENCE

1. H. Ter Meulen and J. Heslinga. *Nouvelles methodes d'analyse chimique*. Dunod, Paris, 1932 pp. 43.

